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To cite this article: Veronica Nieves and Javier Martinez-Amaya 2025 *Environ. Res. Lett.* **20** 114026

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ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH
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OPEN ACCESS

RECEIVED
15 May 2025REVISED
29 September 2025ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION
2 October 2025PUBLISHED
17 October 2025

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AI-driven insights beneath the surface: deeper ocean layers at
play in severe hurricane forecasting

Veronica Nieves* and Javier Martinez-Amaya

Image Processing Laboratory, University of Valencia, 46980 Valencia, Spain

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: Veronica.Nieves@uv.es and Javier.Martinez-Amaya@uv.es**Keywords:** hurricane intensification, extreme weather, subsurface ocean anomalies, AI-driven forecasting, early-warning systemsSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Abstract

Understanding the underexplored role of deeper ocean layers in hurricane dynamics is pivotal amidst escalating storm intensities and growing threats to coastal communities. While early forecasting approaches focused almost exclusively on near-surface variables (e.g. sea surface temperature) or upper-ocean layers (0–100 m), some follow-up efforts integrated subsurface information using ocean heat content analyses relative to the 26 °C isotherm, yielding modest enhancement for the most intense storms. By contrast, our convolutional neural network–random forest (RF) framework explicitly exploits the three-dimensional structure of ocean anomalies from the surface down to 500 m—indirectly capturing heat redistribution, salinity-driven stratification, and mixed-layer dynamics across depths. We demonstrate that the layered information within 40–500 m accounts for $44.91 \pm 0.24\%$ of total variable importance in the RF model and supports 72-h lead-time severe-hurricane forecasts with a precision of $73.04 \pm 7.95\%$. This substantially extends ocean-heat-content-only approaches by: 1) avoiding a hard threshold, 2) providing the first quantification of layer-specific subsurface contributions to severity forecasting through a multi-depth anomaly analysis across multiple variables using an RF-based framework, and 3) leveraging fine-scale spatial patterns via convolutional-neural-network-derived features. Subsurface variables down to 500 m are not merely ancillary—they are indispensable for capturing the ocean precursors of the strongest hurricanes, particularly when the 26 °C isotherm (typically shallower than 100 m) fails to represent the full heat reservoir. This deeper thermal structure may represent a key energy source that can support—and potentially accelerate—severe hurricane intensification. These findings highlight the untapped predictive value of deep-layer ocean information and its potential to enhance early-warning systems for high-impact storm events.

1. Introduction

The importance of predicting extreme weather events is heightened in the context of climate change, particularly for hurricanes over the North Atlantic Ocean and the Northeastern Pacific (IPCC 2023), where recent studies suggest increasing rates of rapid intensification (Bhatia *et al* 2019). These storms are low-pressure systems that pose significant threats to life, infrastructure, and economies, and their non-linear behavior complicates forecasting—especially during rapid development phases, when speeds can change dramatically over a short period.

These shifts often occur under complex conditions, where dynamical-statistical and numerical models face accuracy limitations (Nystrom and Zhang 2019, Cangialosi *et al* 2020, De Maria *et al* 2021) and require substantial computational resources (Chen *et al* 2020).

Artificial intelligence (AI) methods offer a complementary path to hurricane prediction, reducing computational load while improving skill. AI has gained traction in meteorology for its ability to detect non-linear relationships and extract meaningful patterns from high-dimensional datasets (Clutton-Brock *et al* 2021, Chen *et al* 2023, Sandalow *et al* 2024,

Charlton-Perez *et al* 2024). Models such as random forest (RF) and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have shown success analyzing GOES imagery, aiding early detection of rapidly intensifying hurricanes (Martinez-Amaya *et al* 2023a, 2023b). However, applications of AI to ocean-based hurricane prediction remain limited. Some recent studies have employed deep learning to forecast short-term intensity changes using surface features such as sea surface temperature (SST), ocean heat content (OHC), and atmospheric inputs (Xu *et al* 2021).

Subsurface ocean heat plays a critical but often underappreciated role in hurricane intensification. Yet, both AI-based and conventional approaches have primarily focused on surface conditions (e.g. heat fluxes, SST), mixed layer dynamics, thermocline interactions, or OHC estimates relative to the 26 °C isotherm—typically confined to the upper 0–100 m, depending on the region and season (e.g. Shay *et al* 2000, Mainelli *et al* 2008, Alley *et al* 2019). Incorporating subsurface signals extending to 500 m during pre-genesis stages remains largely unexplored—except in some modeling studies (Scoccimarro *et al* 2017)—and represents a significant extension of prior frameworks.

This gap highlights an opportunity to advance predictions by incorporating deeper ocean signals—extending to 500 m—into AI models, moving beyond the upper-ocean-limited focus of prior work. Importantly, while OHC is often estimated relative to the 26 °C isotherm, this threshold does not fully account for deeper layers that sustain ocean-to-atmosphere energy transfer and thereby support continued or rapid intensification. Heat reservoirs stored below the isotherm can re-emerge, especially during rapid-intensification phases, energizing developing storms (Scoccimarro *et al* 2017, 2018); and the fingerprints of underlying subsurface dynamical conditions—whether due to mixing, upwelling, entrainment, mesoscale ocean heat transport (e.g. by the Loop Current and its warm-core eddies), or any combination thereof—provide additional predictive value not captured by upper-ocean metrics alone, as we show in the present study. Furthermore, although valuable, much of the existing research focuses on individual case studies, which limits broader applicability and hinders the development of generalizable insights. To address this, it is necessary to explore multivariate, depth-resolved ocean features—spanning depths to 500 m—across multiple events and examine their relationship with hurricane severity at several pre-peak times. This is particularly relevant for higher-category hurricanes, which are more likely to draw on deep OHC, whereas weaker systems tend to be more sensitive to atmospheric factors such as wind shear and mid-level humidity (e.g. Mainelli *et al* 2008).

This study builds on recent advances in CNN-RF architecture (Martinez-Amaya *et al* 2023b) by integrating vertically resolved ocean data into a hybrid model that couples spatial feature extraction with statistical learning. Our CNN-derived features capture heat stored in the ocean and related properties, offering insights into heat distribution, vertical stratification and mixed-layer dynamics across depths. Unlike conventional predictors based on OHC or SST alone, we include three-dimensional temperature and salinity profiles to examine how subsurface anomalies relate to the likelihood of a storm reaching severe hurricane status. We frame the task as a binary classification problem, with an RF classifier that captures the non-linear links between predictors and storm intensification and serves as the final decision layer. The approach is well suited for distinguishing between two clearly separated categories (tropical storms < Category 1 vs. severe hurricanes \geq Category 3) while avoiding ambiguities from intermediate classes (Categories 1–2). It is important to clarify that the objective is not to forecast tropical cyclone genesis or intensity, but to predict whether an existing storm will intensify into a severe hurricane—i.e. categorical occurrence forecasts at lead time. We hypothesize that AI can learn underlying spatial and vertical features from ocean reanalysis data that precede such events. This approach could support improved early-warning capabilities, particularly during rapid intensification phases, and provide significant value for anticipating catastrophic storm development.

This established CNN-RF methodology is straightforward, interpretable, and avoids subjective assumptions. By advancing feature extraction, classification, and validation, this framework advances AI-based hurricane prediction and deepens understanding of oceanic precursors.

2. Materials and methods

This section describes the integration of hurricane track data, ocean reanalysis, and machine learning methods for severe hurricane prediction, including data sources, preprocessing steps, model architecture, and evaluation metrics.

2.1. Data products and initial steps

We used 3-hourly IBTrACS hurricane track data, including coordinates and wind speeds, for 140 North Atlantic storms (www.ncei.noaa.gov/data/international-best-track-archive-for-climate-stewardship-ibtracs/v04r00/access/). These were grouped into 70 tropical storms (63–118 km h⁻¹; below Category 1) and 70 severe hurricanes (\geq 178 km h⁻¹; Categories 3–5) (Martinez-Amaya *et al* 2023b).

Ocean variables were obtained from the Copernicus Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis product (GLORYS12V1, https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030/description), which provides daily surface and subsurface temperature, salinity (50 vertical levels), and mixed layer depth (MLD) at 1/12° resolution from 1993 onward. GLORYS12V1 reanalysis assimilates satellite-derived sea level anomaly (SLA), SST, and *in situ* temperature–salinity (*T–S*) profiles using advanced filtering and bias correction methods (Lellouche *et al* 2021). Independent evaluations show it accurately reproduces temperature and salinity profiles, captures upper-700 m heat content, and resolves mesoscale variability (Verzemskaia *et al* 2021). Its strong correlation (with coefficients exceeding 0.8) with observed sea surface height (SSH) from altimetry further supports its reliability in representing subsurface thermal structure—making it a robust foundation for assessing ocean conditions down to at least 500 m (Fu *et al* 2023). Moreover, considering that the RF relies on the relative importance of each predictor in forecasting extreme events and joint patterns—rather than absolute magnitudes—our model further limits the impact of modest systematic input biases on its performance. This is further mitigated by the use of anomaly-based predictors and rigorous cross-validation across diverse events (discussed in subsequent sections).

MLD is treated here as an interface variable indicating the thickness of the ocean’s mixed layer (i.e. the depth marking the base of the relatively well-mixed upper-ocean layer, below which stratification intensifies)—rather than as a fixed-depth subsurface variable. For each storm, we computed OHC by integrating temperature from the surface to specified depths (z_i ; see table 1) and calculated vertically averaged temperature and salinity over intervals (z_i-z_{i-1}) within (0–50° N,—110–0° E)—a typical hurricane formation region.

These ocean variables (denoted with X), summarized in table 1, were then cropped within a 10° × 10° box centered on the hurricane’s location 72-h prior to its peak wind speed (Martinez-Amaya *et al* 2023b). The same spatial cropping was applied at the same location 10 d earlier to capture the ocean conditions. Specifically, we analyzed the anomalies—defined as departures from average conditions—at both timepoints (see table 2), calculated as $\Delta X(t) = X_{\text{daily}}(t) - C_{\text{daily}}(t)$, where $C_{\text{daily}}(t)$ is the daily climatology derived by linear interpolation of monthly means (1993–2020 baseline), following NOAA Coral Reef Watch methodology (<https://coralreefwatch.noaa.gov/product/5km/methodology.php>). Monthly climatologies were computed as averages for each calendar month, yielding a seasonally consistent anomaly baseline that is directly comparable across events. These anomalies

Table 1. Ocean variables analyzed using the CNN-RF framework. Includes mixed layer depth (MLD), sea surface temperature (SST) and salinity (SSS), subsurface temperature (T) and salinity (S) averaged over depth intervals (z_i-z_{i-1}), and ocean heat content (OHC) from the surface to z_i . For example, X at 10 m (X_{10m}) denotes the average of X from the surface down to 10 m. OHC is computed by integrating seawater potential temperature from the surface to depths $z_i = 10, 25, 40, 100, 200, 300, 500$ m following TEOS-10 (www.teos-10.org/); the 200 m layer was excluded from the RF model due to collinearity (see section 3.1). All variables are expressed as anomalies relative to the 1993–2020 monthly climatology. The full predictor set comprises 46 features: MLD, SST, SSS, 6 OHC values, and 14 T and S layers (7 each)—all computed at two timeframes (ΔX_{-3d} and ΔX_{diff}) as discussed below.

Variable	Description
MLD	Ocean mixed layer depth (Base of well-mixed upper ocean)
OHC (z_i)	Integrated temperature within depth z_i (Total heat stored from the surface down to depth z_i)
SST, SSS	Sea surface temperature and salinity (Temperature and salinity of the surface ocean)
$T(z_i)$	Vertically averaged temperature within z_i to z_{i-1} (Average temperature between depths z_{i-1} and z_i)
$S(z_i)$	Vertically averaged salinity within z_i to z_{i-1} (Average salinity between depths z_{i-1} and z_i)

capture atypical ocean conditions relevant to hurricane development at two key timepoints:

- (1) ΔX_{-3d} , the anomaly at $T_{\text{peak}}-3d$ (72-h before peak intensity, where T_{peak} is the time of maximum sustained wind speed), and
- (2) $\Delta X_{\text{diff}} = \Delta X_{-3d} - \Delta X_{-13d}$, the change in anomaly between $T_{\text{peak}}-3d$ and $T_{\text{peak}}-13d$, reflecting evolving subsurface conditions over the prior 10 d.

The 10 d window was chosen to capture meaningful pre-intensification changes that may signal readiness for severe development, and early-warning potential, without implying that conditions at $T_{\text{peak}}-13d$ are more influential than those at $T_{\text{peak}}-3d$. Tests with longer intervals (e.g. 20–40 d) showed negligible difference. The 72-h reference aligns with the typical hurricane lifespan, often shorter than three days.

Next, to examine spatial patterns across these timeframes—and building on the work of Martinez-Amaya *et al* (2023b)—we applied a single CNN to the cropped ocean anomaly fields. While this approach was previously used to analyze evolving cloud structures from GOES imagery in the Pacific and Atlantic

Table 2. Timepoint definitions for severe hurricane forecasting framework. Key temporal references relative to peak intensity (T_{peak}): $T_{\text{peak}} - 3\text{d}$ (72-h mark) and $T_{\text{peak}} - 13\text{d}$ (start of the 10 d window for anomaly change).

Symbol/ Term	Meaning
T_{peak}	Time of hurricane peak intensity (maximum sustained wind)
$T_{\text{peak}} - 3\text{d}$	72-h lead time before peak (model input point)
$T_{\text{peak}} - 13\text{d}$	10 d before the 72-h lead time (used to compute anomaly changes)
$T_{\text{peak}} + 2\text{d}$	2 d after peak intensity (used in anomaly map visualization only)

(Martinez-Amaya *et al* 2023b), the focus here shifts to detecting oceanic precursors. For CNN input, the anomaly fields were resized to 128×128 pixels via bilinear interpolation to match the model's fixed input size, and standardized using Z -score normalization (zero mean, unit variance) to ensure consistent scaling across input variables. This method, common in geospatial analysis, effectively captures fine-scale spatial patterns while remaining scalable to large datasets (Lee *et al* 2020, Maskey *et al* 2020, Carmo *et al* 2021).

The CNN architecture matches that of Martinez-Amaya *et al* (2023b), consisting of three convolutional layers (5×5 , 3×3 , and 3×3 filters), each followed by max-pooling (to reduce dimensionality while retaining key spatial patterns) and ReLU activation functions (to capture non-linear interactions), and a fully connected layer outputting a 32-neuron feature vector representation per variable. Regularization techniques—dropout (0.65) and batch normalization—helped prevent overfitting. Hyperparameters (e.g. learning rate, batch size) were optimized through manual tuning based on cross-validation performance, selecting a batch size of 16 and learning rate of 0.001. The final output is a single representative value (one per variable/depth/timeframe) capturing fine-scale spatial patterns in ocean anomalies—which we refer to as *CNN-derived features*. These features are concatenated as a multi-dimensional input vector, which is then used to train the RF model (described in the next section). An overview of the full data-to-model flow—including spatial and temporal processing, anomaly extraction, and CNN-RF integration—is shown in figure 1.

This approach leverages spatial patterns while maintaining interpretability, as the CNN is used for feature extraction rather than classification. Unlike the CNN-RF framework in Martinez-Amaya *et al* (2023b), this variant omits temporal integration and instead relies on anomaly differences between two

fixed pre-peak windows to characterize subsurface ocean precursors. We found this strategy to yield better performance in the ocean context. It also avoids temporal smoothing or stacking, preserving physical meaning across depth and time. Accordingly, the analysis focuses on spatial patterns at two fixed stages of pre-intensification. The study period spans 1993–2020, consistent with the availability of ocean data.

2.2. AI-driven classification, prediction, and evaluation framework

Our CNN–RF model adaptation of Martinez-Amaya *et al* (2023b) was trained on a balanced set of 70 severe hurricanes and 70 tropical storms from 1993–2020, a design that maximizes contrast, removes label ambiguity and avoids class-imbalance bias—a widely adopted strategy in extreme-event machine-learning studies (Biswas and Sinha 2021, Martinez-Amaya *et al* 2023b).

The CNN-derived features—summarizing fine-scale spatial ocean anomalies at multiple depths—serve as input to the RF classifier, composed of up to 100 decision trees, with the number tuned to performance saturation (Martinez-Amaya *et al* 2023b). Here, the RF evaluates precursor ocean conditions at two key pre-peak timepoints ($T_{\text{peak}} - 3\text{d}$ and $T_{\text{peak}} - 13\text{d}$). Each tree is trained on a different data subset to reduce overfitting. The dataset was split into training and testing sets (80%–20%), following Martinez-Amaya *et al* (2023b). Final predictions are made via majority voting (Martinez-Amaya *et al* 2023b).

RF outperforms other methods, including CNN, on small datasets due to its robustness against overfitting. Thus, CNN is used solely for feature extraction. While RF offers interpretability, it operates within a hybrid architecture where inputs are derived from a multi-depth CNN anomaly encoder that captures spatiotemporal ocean patterns. This layered setup balances predictive power with interpretability, identifying key ocean features and depths linked to severe hurricane development—supporting both robustness and operational value.

Our experimental setup and evaluation metrics replicate those of Martinez-Amaya *et al* (2023b), demonstrating the framework's versatility to adapt to diverse forecasting contexts. To ensure reliability and minimize bias, we applied k -fold cross-validation, iteratively training and validating across data subsets to improve generalization. This yields 72-h lead-time occurrence predictions—forecasts made 72-h before peak intensity—based on ocean variables at $T_{\text{peak}} - 3\text{d}$ and their 10 day changes, evaluated here in hindcast using reanalysis inputs. Once trained, the CNN-RF framework enables efficient, low-cost inference from daily ocean updates, allowing timely hurricane risk assessments with minimal computational demand (Martinez-Amaya *et al* 2023b). While GLORYS12V1

was used here as a proof-of-concept hindcast, the same predictor set can be supplied from real-time analysis or forecast fields for operational implementation. Prospective use would require routine bias calibration to account for product-specific systematics. However, because predictors are anomalies and storm-aligned patterns, transferability depends on learned relationships rather than direct values, supporting use with other data sources. In addition, the framework supports continuously refreshed forecasts, since it can be rerun whenever new data become available—valuable since subsurface heat anomalies often signal rapid intensification before atmospheric cues appear (e.g. Shay *et al* 2000, Liu *et al* 2025).

In practice, the model can be rerun with each data update, forecasting severe status 72-h ahead based on current ocean conditions—without requiring prior knowledge of a storm’s future intensity. Although training labels are aligned to T_{peak} , no future information is used at inference. This causal setup reflects a true forecasting workflow; however, the present study evaluates that workflow using retrospective inputs. The RF is also computationally efficient, supporting timely predictions in rapidly evolving environments (Martinez-Amaya *et al* 2023b). While this study focuses on the 72-h lead, separate models could target other lead times, as features are extractable at any point. Still, capturing precursors 72-h before peak is particularly challenging—and valuable—which this

study demonstrates. This supports a flexible early-warning system, as shown in Martinez-Amaya *et al* (2023a, 2023b).

This approach balances model accuracy and interpretability. Model performance was benchmarked against observed outcomes, providing an objective evaluation using several canonical metrics: precision (p), which reflects performance on the severe-hurricane class, and Cohen’s kappa (κ), a chance-adjusted agreement score across both severe and non-severe events—both metrics are defined below (Martinez-Amaya *et al* 2023a, 2023b). No direct comparison with other existing models (e.g. Xu *et al* 2021) was attempted, as our framework differs in predictors, targets, architecture, and goals, making such comparisons inappropriate and potentially misleading. Our focus is not on outperforming others in precision but on demonstrating the unique predictive value of deeper ocean layers (down to 500 m)—a contribution not previously quantified.

Precision measures the share of true positives (TP) among positive predictions (TP + FP): $p = \text{TP}/(\text{TP} + \text{FP})$. Here, TP are correctly predicted severe hurricanes, and FP are incorrect severe predictions (false positives). Because the false-alarm ratio ($\text{FAR} = \text{FP}/[\text{TP} + \text{FP}]$) satisfies $\text{precision} = 1 - \text{FAR}$, false alarms are quantified in the same confusion-matrix space. Thus, precision directly reflects the model’s ability to identify severe hurricanes while

keeping false positives low—critical for early-warning systems, where unnecessary alarms can erode trust and waste resources. Emphasizing precision therefore limits over-warnings while maintaining sensitivity to real threats. Complementary to precision, Cohen's κ adjusts for the accuracy expected by random chance, providing agreement beyond mere coincidence: $\kappa = 2 \times (TP \times TN - FN \times FP) / [(TP + FP) \times (FP + TN) + (TP + FN) \times (FN + TN)]$, where TN are correctly predicted non-severe events (true negatives) and FN are missed severe hurricanes (false negatives). Overall accuracy was also computed during cross-validation (reported as mean \pm standard deviation)—alongside precision and Cohen's κ —to give a full picture of model performance.

To identify key ocean predictors, we computed the RF's built-in feature-importance scores (Python 3.11.4; scikit-learn v1.2.1 *feature_importances_* attribute), which rank each input variable by its contribution to classification accuracy. Variable importance in RFs reflects each predictor's relative contribution to reducing impurity across all trees. Importantly, predictors are not treated as independent; RF models capture non-linear interactions among features, so importance scores reflect marginal contributions within a multivariate context. This ranking quantifies the influence of subsurface conditions across depths and timeframes in driving severe intensification—even if precision cannot be directly compared to mixed-variable or atmospheric-dominated forecasting models.

Finally, we evaluated model skill on independent case studies (e.g. Hurricanes Michael, Jose, Irma) to assess generalization to unseen events using the hit ratio (HR = TP/[TP + FN]), which measures successful forecasts for unseen events. Missed events lower HR values, reflecting sensitivity to false negatives. While precision is our primary metric, HR plays the recall-like role for independent severe cases (the corresponding false-detection ratio is simply $1 - \text{HR}$, so it is already captured by the reported HR values).

3. Results

3.1. Unlocking the role of subsurface patterns: the hidden drivers shaping severe hurricanes

Our RF model is designed to identify 'lowest-common-denominator' predictors that consistently contribute to classification skill across a large number of events. It does not isolate ocean-type-specific signatures or resolve storm-specific physical mechanisms. Accordingly, we refrain from assigning definitive causal explanations and instead interpret the results in terms of plausible, physically grounded scenarios.

Overall, the five-fold cross-validated RF model at a 72-h lead, using all 46 ocean features (figure 2), achieves a mean precision of $73.04 \pm 7.95\%$ and a Cohen's κ of 0.48 ± 0.09 (see [Methods](#)), providing

a concise summary of model skill. This performance shows that the model can reliably identify severe hurricanes using only ocean data—particularly valuable for early-warning systems, where minimizing false positives (false-alarm ratio $< 30\%$, i.e. well below chance) is essential. The κ value confirms moderate agreement beyond chance—and borders on 'substantial' depending on the upper bound—consistent with solidly meaningful classification skill across the dataset.

The predictor importance analysis showed that changes in MLD were the most influential factor among all ocean predictors in hurricane development during the 10 day period leading up to the 72-h mark before peak intensity. This finding reinforces the importance of accounting for temporal changes in MLD in predictive models to improve accuracy (figure 2). These changes contributed $14.50 \pm 1.37\%$, slightly higher than the $11.33 \pm 2.44\%$ from the 72-h anomalies, though their uncertainty bounds overlap (figure 2, right and left panels). The Atlantic MLD typically ranges from 30 to over 150 m deep (Buckley and Marshall 2016), with variability driven by changes in solar heating, wind, thermal stratification, ocean currents, and surface heat fluxes. Its depth is often capped by the thermocline, which limits vertical mixing. A deeper thermocline allows a thicker mixed layer, enhancing the available heat reservoir and potentially fueling intensification (Shay *et al* 2000). This variability is critical, as it governs heat transfer and directly affects hurricane strength (Mainelli *et al* 2008). While the barrier layer is not explicitly included—due to storm-specific definitions not scalable to multi-event datasets—its effects may be partially captured through stratification derived from vertically averaged salinity and temperature. These features reflect the physical structure known to influence barrier layer formation and vertical mixing limitation (Sprintall and Tomczak 1992, Balaguru *et al* 2012). Warm- and cool-phase years of the Atlantic multidecadal oscillation (AMO) can precondition upper-ocean structure and reduce vertical wind shear, favoring hurricane intensification (Zhang and Delworth 2006). However, our anomaly-based RF model focuses on event-scale deviations that remain robust to these multidecadal background shifts.

Another key factor is temperature within specific layers at the 72-h mark. Vertically averaged temperatures were more predictive than OHC, which integrates over the column and can mask opposing signals from different layers. Notably, there is prominent influence from the 40–500 m temperature group, reflecting the vertically coherent thermal structure of intensification-related processes within this part of the subsurface ocean. Even though OHC's upper bound slightly overlaps mean temperature's lower contribution ($2.65 \pm 0.40\%$), its entire range ($0.52 \pm 0.08\%$ to $2.50 \pm 0.31\%$) remains below,

making temperature the stronger predictor. In addition, preliminary tests showed that including OHC at 200 m alongside neighboring layers (e.g. 300 m) introduced collinearity that diluted feature rankings without improving model performance. To maintain parsimony and interpretability, we retained only the OHC layers with stronger and more distinct contributions. As expected, the predictive contribution of subsurface temperature and OHC was lower over the 10 d window than at the 72-h mark, when deeper layers likely serve as the primary heat source—via, for example, vertical mixing or upwelling. Yet contributions in these layers persisted at both timeframes, with net heat extending several hundred meters deep. While not always the dominant factor, deep-layer heat remains highly relevant and deserves greater attention in hurricane prediction. This aligns with Scoccimarro *et al* (2017), who noted that storm-ocean interactions can reach depths of 1000 m in high-resolution coupled models. However, this contrasts with case-specific observational studies (Sanford *et al* 2011), which often limit impacts to the upper 100 m.

Our results also highlight the predictive value of salinity—both anomalies and 10 d-prior changes—throughout the upper 500 m (figure 2). Anomalies contributed $23.46 \pm 0.95\%$ overall (with the 0–10 m layer accounting for $13.39 \pm 2.56\%$), while changes contributed $21.04 \pm 0.60\%$ (with the 40–100 m layer accounting for $11.26 \pm 1.91\%$). Remarkably, these two salinity predictors rank among the top five single-feature contributors overall, underscoring their outsized role in distinguishing severe from non-severe hurricanes across all events. Salinity affects surface buoyancy and stratification, which can promote or suppress vertical transport of heat—in particular, near-surface stratification may help retain heat

in layers accessible to storms, while deeper salinity anomalies can signal barrier-layer formation that maintains a stable thermal structure favorable for energy uptake. These underlying dynamics are complex and highly localized (Balaguru *et al* 2020, Chen *et al* 2020).

Taken together, our data-driven assessment confirms the critical role of upper-ocean salinity structure and MLD, while also highlighting the often-overlooked contribution of deeper thermal features as robust indicators of intensification potential—with variables from 40–500 m collectively accounting for $44.91 \pm 0.24\%$ of total feature importance ($37.18 \pm 0.25\%$ within the 100–500 m subset). A key point is that these results emerge from statistically consistent patterns across all events—not from assumptions or hand-picked inputs.

3.2. Hurricane Michael: a spotlight on deep heat transfer

To further assess practical value, we applied the pre-trained 72-h model to three independent severe-hurricane cases—Michael (2018), Jose (2017), and Irma (2017)—all excluded from training. Evaluated with the HR metric (see [Methods](#)), the model achieved success rates $\geq 80\%$ (80% for Jose and Michael; 100% for Irma), indicating correct severestatus forecasts in at least four of the five-fold models. This demonstrates the approach’s adaptability and robustness across diverse ocean-atmosphere interaction scenarios.

Hurricane Michael (7–11 October 2018) in particular exemplifies the critical role of deep-heat contributions and salinity-stratification to storm intensification and near-peak surface cooling patterns, as revealed by our variable-importance

AI analysis, which consistently identifies these signals across the wider hurricane dataset. Given that, for Hurricane Michael, both the temperature layers and OHC exhibited clear, coherent deep heat-uptake patterns along the storm track, we display only the temperature panel at 500 m here as a representative heat signal of its full extent, though strongest within the 40–300 m layers (see figure 3 and supplemental figure 1 for the full depth sequence; markers indicate the hurricane's position at 24 h intervals). For this case, we present two-dimensional anomaly difference maps over the period from $T_{\text{peak}}-13\text{d}$ (10 d before the 72-h forecast) through $T_{\text{peak}}+2\text{d}$ (2 d after peak intensity, where peak is denoted by an asterisk in figure 3). Including these two post-peak days provides a clearer snapshot of how ocean properties evolve during the storm's evolution, prior to CNN-RF analysis.

The temperature map at 500 m (bottom panel, figure 3) reflects a dynamically active column extending to 500 m, with heterogeneous patterns and sharp gradients indicative of strong variability and activity—analogue to those observed beneath other intense storms (Shay *et al* 2000, Mainelli *et al* 2008). In contrast, the surface layer exhibits more localized anomalies (top panel, figure 3; see also supplemental figure 1). Although mesoscale structures (e.g. eddies, fronts) can modulate ocean anomalies, our analysis focuses on spatially and temporally aligned patterns along the hurricane trajectory—thereby minimizing the influence of unrelated background variability. This alignment of storm position and thermal features enables clearer interpretation across different storm phases. Subsurface heat from deeper layers is likely redistributed upward through vertical mixing and upwelling, with Loop Current anticyclonic rings maintaining anomalously thick warm layers that limited the cooling during the storm's passage (Le Hénaff *et al* 2021, Schönau *et al* 2024)—fueling intensification in ways that support cross-layer energy exchange, while modulating SST response and modifying MLD structure (through deepening and shoaling) (see supplemental figure 1).

In post-peak phases, surface layers release heat to the atmosphere, leading to surface cooling (figure 3), which also reflects the cold-wake effect—vertical mixing driven by hurricane winds that upwells cooler water—an effect documented for Michael's case by Schönau *et al* (2024). However, our analysis focuses on pre-peak conditions, where stratified temperature anomalies at depth and OHC down to 500 m (as seen in supplemental figure 1) support the hypothesis that subsurface heat contributes to storm intensification via ocean-to-atmosphere energy transfer. The clear spatial alignment between surface and deeper thermal features along the storm track supports vertical heat redistribution.

Although less central to our conclusions about deeper-layer thermal signatures, observed salinity increases at 40–100 m along the pre-peak portion of the storm track primarily coincide with reduced temperature and OHC near the Gulf entrance (first two markers, supplemental figure 1), suggesting an adjustment of the incoming Loop Current. This pre-condition occurs within a regional setting where subsurface salinity maxima near ~ 150 m are characteristic of Loop Current anticyclonic eddies, while the Mississippi River plume supplies fresher surface waters that create strong salinity gradients in the northern Gulf (Oey *et al* 2005, Da Silva and Castelao 2018), thereby maintaining upper-ocean heat in layers accessible to storms. As the storm approaches peak strength, hurricane-driven mixing typically erodes this structure and homogenizes the upper ocean, with surface salinity rising from underlying saltier layers rather than direct evaporation.

These combined observations highlight the interplay of vertical mixing, stratification, and air-sea feedbacks that support storm intensification, underscoring the value of including both surface and subsurface ocean conditions in forecasting models.

4. Summary

Our results demonstrate the value of AI methods in revealing how deep-layer ocean conditions precede occurrences of severe hurricanes. By analyzing subsurface ocean properties across several hundred meters, this study highlights the role of heat redistribution in storm intensification. These findings show that, even without atmospheric inputs, an ocean-only classifier can deliver 72-h forecasts of severe hurricane events, providing early warning of rapid development and complementing conventional numerical weather prediction—particularly in challenging intensification scenarios.

The integration of CNN-extracted anomaly features with an RF model provided insights into which ocean precursors matter most—MLD, subsurface salinity, and temperature anomalies—across depths to 500 m. This deep-layer analysis extends beyond most current forecasting systems, paving the way for further research into underexplored subsurface processes. The results validate that including layered subsurface data—grounded in the physics of hurricane dynamics, especially heat redistribution and salinity-related stratification—elevates these variables as essential predictors rather than sources of redundancy. Moreover, the rigorous cross-validation procedure confirms model robustness and minimizes overfitting, ensuring a balance between interpretability, performance, and computational efficiency for reliable forecasts.

Relying solely on oceanic precursors provides an efficient complement to traditional dynamical modeling, with lower computational demands. This approach enriches decision-support pipelines for at-risk coastal regions, supports enhanced preparedness for extreme weather events, and contributes to the evolving needs of real-time operational forecasting in a warming climate.

By continuously updating the model with new ocean data, this framework remains adaptive. Its flexibility supports evolving hurricane risk assessments and enables timely integration into early-warning systems based on interpretable, ocean-driven predictors—especially during critical pre-intensification phases.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL: <https://github.com/AI4OCEANS/>.

Acknowledgments

This research was jointly supported by the European Space Agency (Contract 4000134529/21/NL/GLC/my) and the Ministry of Education, Culture, Universities, and Employment (Grant CIDEAGENT/2019/055).

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest related to this work.

Author contributions

Veronica Nieves 0000-0003-0024-8383
Conceptualization (lead), Data curation (equal), Formal analysis (equal), Funding acquisition (lead), Investigation (lead), Methodology (equal), Project administration (lead), Supervision (lead), Validation (equal), Visualization (equal), Writing – original draft (equal), Writing – review & editing (lead)

Javier Martinez-Amaya 0000-0001-6436-3845
Data curation (equal), Formal analysis (equal), Investigation (supporting), Methodology (equal), Validation (equal), Visualization (equal), Writing – original draft (equal)

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